

HIGH THERMAL CONDUCTIVITY OF THIN-WALL INJECTION MOLDED PARTS FOR ALN/PBT COMPOSITES

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1 Introduction

Downsizing and concentration of electrical components continue in electrical and information industries. However, concentration of the components generates great heat inside a device. For that reason, a rapid cooling system must be constructed to improve the device performance. In general, polymers have high formability and low heat conductivity. Recently, a new polymer alloy system with good thermal properties was produced by compounding fillers that have high heat conductivity. These composites have high formability and heat conductivity. Moreover, high electric insulation is necessary for electrical devices, rendering carbon-based fillers such as graphite and carbon fibers unsuitable. Ceramic fillers are attractive candidates in this regard because they can provide the necessary thermal diffusivity while retaining the polymers' qualities of electrical insulation and high formability. Numerous ceramic fillers have high thermal diffusivity: aluminum oxide, aluminum nitride, silicon nitride, silicon carbide, and magnesium oxide. Nevertheless, these materials would damage the molds during injection molding. Aluminum nitride (AlN), an inorganic material, is a white ceramic with several crystal structures. AlN potential for application in microelectronics was realized due to its relative high thermal conductivity for an electrical insulating ceramic ($70\text{--}210\text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$ for polycrystalline material, and as high as $285\text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$ for single crystals). Especially, AlN fiber is filled to polymer materials; such polymer composites show softness, electrical isolation, high temperature stability, high chemical resistance, and high heat conductivity.

Recently we performed thin-wall injection molding for polypropylene/hexagonal boron nitride

(PP/h-BN). Then we analyzed the processability and higher-order structure of thin parts for PP/h-BN composites [1–4].

In this study, the processability and higher-order structure of thin-wall parts with AlN fiber filled polymer composites as a matrix polymer of poly(butylene terephthalate) (PBT) were investigated to produce new polymer composites with high heat diffusivity. Effects of AlN fiber composition and process parameters on processability, thermal property, and internal morphology of parts were discussed.

2 Experimental

2.1 Material

We used poly(butylene terephthalate) (PBT, Novaduran, 5010R5; Mitsubishi Engineering-Plastics Corporation) as matrix polymer and aluminum nitride (AlN) fibers with high aspect ratio (length/diameter) ($100\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ initial length and ca. $5\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ diameter; Mitsubishi Chemical Gr.) as filler material. AlN fibers obtained nitriding ratio 95% over under optimum treatment. Figure 1 presents SEM image of the fiber.

Fig. 1 SEM picture of AlN fibers.

2.2 Compounding, molding process and mold

We compounded PBT and AlN using a twin-screw micro-compounding system (Imoto Seisakushi Co.) by compounding the temperature at 260°C with compounding time at 10 min. The compositions of AlN were 20 and 40 vol%.

A small electric injection-molding machine (ELJECT AU3E; Nissei Plastic Industrial Co., Ltd.) was used in this system for molding. In injection molding of thin-wall plates, the injection unit temperature, the mold temperature, the holding pressure, the maximum injection pressure, and cavity thickness were, respectively, 265°C, 140°C, 50 MPa, 200 MPa, and 0.3 or 1 mm. The injection speed was selected to 120 or 160 mm/s. Figure 2 shows photograph of PBT/AlN composites product. The flow length of molded parts decreased with increasing composition of AlN. At 1.0 mm thickness, the flow length of molded parts increased; then showed a full pack.

Figure 2 Photographs of products of PBT/AlN composites. Cavity thickness is 0.3mm. Injection speed is 120 mm/s.

Injection compression molding (ICM) was also performed to improve the thermal properties of the composites. In ICM process, the molecular orientation inside molded parts was reduced as compared with a common injection molding process. One of research objects in this study is to improve thermal conductivity for thickness direction of molded parts. In this process, the injection unit temperature, the mold temperature, the holding

pressure, the maximum injection pressure, and cavity thickness were, respectively, 265°C, 140°C, 50 MPa, 200 MPa, and 0.3 mm. The injection speed was selected to 300 mm/s. The compression stroke as cavity open distance was varied at 0.5 and 2.0 mm. The plunger position for compression reached at 0.5 or 2.5 mm, and then the compression for cavity started immediately. This means that compression delay time was 0 s. Figure 3 shows photographs of PBT/AlN composites products of injection compression molding. In ICM, the flow length increased and the composites filled perfectly as compared with a common injection molding products (#4). At 20 vol%, the composites also filled in the cavity at all molding condition.

Figure 3 Photographs of products of PBT/AlN ICM composites.

#1: the compression stroke 0.5 mm & the plunger position for compression 2.5 mm

#2: the compression stroke 2.0 mm & the plunger position for compression 0.5 mm

#3: the compression stroke 2.0 mm & the plunger position for compression 2.5 mm

#4: the compression stroke 0 mm (common injection molding)

2.3 Characteristic method

We investigated the processability through the flow length of the thin-wall plate. Thermal properties of PBT/AlN composites were measured using modulated DSC and TGA measurements. Thermal diffusivity of the thin plate along the thickness direction (ND direction) was measured using a temperature wave-analysis system. The higher-order structure of the thin plate was evaluated using wide angle X-ray diffraction (WAXD)

measurements. We also observed filler distribution and orientation inside cross sectional areas of products using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) after freezing with liquid N₂ and splitting along the MD line. Tensile tests were conducted using a mini tensile testing machine after the thin plate was cut into a dumbbell shape.

3 Results and Discussion

We observed the cross-sectional area of the PBT thin-wall product near the gate by SEM. Figure 4 presents an SEM image of the cross-sectional area of the PBT thin-wall product near the gate, which contains 40 vol% AlN. The filler aligned along the polymer flow direction and laminar structure of PBT/AlN was observed. The filler orientation along the MD axis was higher at the product edge than at the product center. It was apparently equal to that of the skin-shear-core layer inside the injection molding products. The AlN orientation near the surface became higher than that of the product center. The polymer flow near the cavity wall shows high shear stress attributable to rapid cooling.

Therefore, the injection molded product revealed a structural distribution inside the cross-sectional area. The AlN orientation was observed directly using SEM. The polymer orientation is usually evaluated by optical retardation. However, the product was unclear; we evaluated the polymer orientation using the WAXD image.

Figure 5 shows WAXD images of products of PBT/AlN composites. From the WAXD measurement, the flow direction of PBT molded product was aligned parallel to the meridian direction of the WAXD image. The crystalline peak was assigned to the equatorial direction if the molecular oriented to the flow direction. The peak intensity also concentrated to the equatorial position. However, the pattern became broader with increasing distance from the gate, indicating that the pressure distribution in the cavity influenced the development of the higher-order structure. In general, pressure in the cavity decreases downstream. The polymer orientation similarly decreases downstream. The diffraction pattern of PBT/AlN composite became broader than that of product PBT only.

Effects of compounding AlN on mechanical

Figure 4 SEM picture of the cross-sectional area of the PBT/ AlN composites.

Figure 5 WAXD images of PBT/AlN composites. Injection speed is 120 mm/s.

properties of thin-wall products are much higher than those of changing the injection speed. Increasing the AlN contents engenders modulus improvement, equal strength, and greatly decreased elongation at the break. The stress–strain curve of the thin-wall product of PBT revealed a typical ductile deformation curve. However, no yielding point was visible in the stress–strain curve of the thin-wall product of the PBT/AlN composite, i.e. a typical ductile deformation curve was obtained. This tendency reflects that a change of the breaking mechanism occurred by compounding AlN.

Effects of injection speed and filler composition on thermal diffusivity of the PBT/AlN thin-wall products are portrayed in Figure 6. Almost four-times-greater thermal diffusivity was achieved in the case of AlN content 40 vol%. It is necessary to form a network using fillers to improve the thermal diffusivity of composites by compounding fillers. The layer of AlN fillers in the PBT matrix was structured in the injection molding process, as portrayed in SEM images. Therefore, the PBT layer blocked heat flow along the thickness direction and the thin-wall plate seemed to reveal anisotropic thermal diffusivity. Thermal diffusivity along the thickness direction is greatly increased if isotropic shapes of fillers are used. However, in the case of fiber filler, thermal diffusivity at the flow end was higher than that at the gate position.

Figure 7 shows the effect of filler composition on thermal diffusivity of the injection compression molding PBT/AlN thin-wall products. Six-times-greater thermal diffusivity was achieved as compared with only PBT products. The thermal diffusivity also showed higher values as compared with injection molding products. From the SEM observation of cross-sectional area of the products, it was found that AlN orientation near the surface became random.

4 Conclusions

We investigated the processability, structure, and properties of PBT/AlN composite using thin-wall products. Results show that the polymer orientation decreased. Strength and elongation at the break of molded parts were lowered, but the modulus was greatly improved. Thermal diffusivity and thermal diffusivity increased concomitantly with increasing AlN fiber contents. However, the thermal property was dependent upon the polymer and AlN fiber

orientation. It is important to control the AlN orientation for improvement of heat-release characteristics. Overall, high processability and thermal properties were achieved using the polymer/AlN composites.

5 References

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Figure 6 Thermal diffusivity of the PBT/AlN thin-wall products at various positions.

Figure 7 Thermal diffusivity of the injection compression molding PBT/AlN products. These conditions see figure's caption 3